

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

THIRD PATTERN POLICY BRIEF

PATTERN.

Empowering Open and Responsible
Research and Innovation

Policy Brief building on the overall project results to support training coordinators with co-designed solutions and recommendations for efficient embedding of the training on Open RRI themes for students and researchers at different career stages at institutional level.

18 June 2026

INTRODUCTION

The EU-funded PATTERN project advances innovative approaches to equip students and researchers with societally relevant and future-oriented skills in Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI) while strengthening the institutional capacity in universities and research institutions. The project emphasizes eight key transferable skills, including Open Access (OA); FAIR Research Data Management; Citizen Science; Research Integrity; Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research; Science Communication; and Mental Health and Leadership. Getting and applying this knowledge supports researchers' intersectoral mobility, social responsibility of science and fosters inclusive and participatory research lifecycles and processes. These efforts align with the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2025-2027¹, which aims to build a sustainable, digital, and resilient Europe grounded in excellence, ethics, inclusiveness, and trust in science. Within this context, PATTERN co-designed and piloted high-quality Open RRI trainings, supported its widespread adoption and reusability, facilitated institutional integration, strengthened the training delivery capacities, and stimulated changes in research culture in the long run.

The Third PATTERN Policy Brief relies on the overall project results, including two learning cycles (LCs) which were respectively the testing and the refining phases for PATTERN training in 14 pilot institutions. While the first LC (LC1) was piloted within consortium institutions, the second LC (LC2) was open to external participants, enabling the engagement of students and researchers from a wide range of countries and institutions beyond the consortium. It also builds on co-creation through the Open Studio methodology, involving participation of the PATTERN consortium, both within and beyond the project teams, as well as trainers and training coordinators from within and outside the consortium.

¹ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/era-policy-agenda-2025-2027>

This Policy Brief provides a series of concrete solutions and recommendations aimed at training coordinators and other staff members in charge of providing institutional support for embedding the Open RRI training, with the goal of enhancing learning journeys through modular, flexible, and career-stage based offerings.

EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS

Within LC1 (May 2024 – April 2025), PATTERN developed and piloted eight modular training courses (one per Open RRI thematic area) across 14 European universities and research institutions that are consortium members. These pilots were evaluated using a rigorous monitoring, evaluation and learning framework drawing on established program evaluation methodologies². A multi-dimensional evaluation assessed, among other aspects, the learner satisfaction, learning outcomes, and early signs of institutional impact. This continuous evaluation process informed the refinement of the training strategy for LC2.

Within LC2 (May 2025 – April 2026), the training sessions were delivered in more focused persona (career stage)-based cohorts to encourage active participation, while interactive and blended learning methods were expanded through case-based activities, problem-solving scenarios, advanced content and personalised learning tools. Course materials and sessions were readjusted and opened to the external public. These materials are hosted on the OpenPlato platform³, which offers advanced features and tailored learning pathways to ensure accessibility, adaptability, flexibility, and sustainability. At the same time, the Projects platform⁴ was enriched with real-world case scenarios, while resources were localised and translated to support inclusive, multilingual, and context-specific delivery. A train-the-trainer approach, coordinated scheduling, and alignment with key policy priorities such as inclusivity, research integrity, FAIR data, further strengthened institutional uptake and ensured relevance to Horizon Europe and ERA expectations.

The outcomes, specificities and challenges of designing, improving and delivering the training, integrating it into curricula and the needs for institutional support in the long term were discussed in depth during the final, third Open Studio cycle⁵, composed of two online sessions (November 2025 and March 2026) and a physical session (April 2026, Brussels). The co-creation methodology guided the participants through phases of open discussion and brainstorming (*divergence*) and subsequent concretising of the ideas as well as validating and fine-tuning them (*convergence*). Participation of trainers and training coordinators from within and beyond the consortium partner institutions, brought an added value to the co-creation process and enabled a broader exchange of perspectives and practices applicable across different career stages as well as the development of action plans and methods that are transferable and adaptable across contexts.

The LCs and the Open Studio co-creation workshops' outcomes identified the following critical challenges:

- ***Designing and sustaining Open RRI training.*** A key issue is the lack of systematic follow-up, driven by limited trainers' capacity, fragmented training modules and support materials, as well as weak institutional support. Integrating content into curricula remains uneven, and time constraints make it difficult to deliver full modules or maintain interdisciplinarity across diverse learner backgrounds.

² Koller, K., & Marschalek, I. (2025). D3.3 Evaluation of outcomes and refinement strategy (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15209490>

³ <https://openplato.eu/blocks/catalog/list.php#block-taggedcoursesearch-searchform>

⁴ <https://pattern.projects.directory/categories/?page=1>

⁵ Two previous Open Studio cycles' (conducted in 2024 and 2025 respectively) outcomes served as basis for previous PATTERN Policy Briefs: Salnikova, A., Brandstetter-Kunc, A., & Ipolyi, I. (2024). D4.2 First PATTERN Policy Brief (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10998470>; and Salnikova, A., Brandstetter-Kunc, A., & Bara-Busila, I. (2025). D4.3 Second PATTERN Policy Brief (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15296911>

- ***Engagement***. PhD students and researchers often show low motivation in mandatory courses, while linguistic diversity and disciplinary specificities complicate delivery. Senior faculty participation is limited, reinforcing a growing knowledge gap between early-career researchers and their supervisors.
- ***Institutional and policy barriers***. Many Open RRI courses are not formally recognised or rewarded, limiting their value for career progression. Trainers also face tensions between learners’ interests and what supervisors expect, as well as challenges in defining quality standards, ensuring accessibility, and conducting meaningful assessments.
- ***Intersectorial mobility***. Non-academic career paths are still considered by many researchers as a “second choice” or even a failure. Insufficient involvement of Quadruple Helix actors in co-assessing what research-related skills, including Open RRI skills, reflect the best their own and labour market needs, leads to poor understanding of Open RRI skills transferability and applicability.

The findings and corresponding recommendations for addressing the identified challenges and for embedding Open RRI training across the various career stages are presented below. They are designed for training coordinators and similar roles within universities and research institutions and are organised around the distinct needs of each EURAXESS career stage (R1-R4)⁶.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. EARLY CAREER RESEARCHERS (R1)

Early career researchers (R1) engage with Open RRI training mostly when it is formally recognised through ECTS or clear credentials. Without credits, certificates or badges, R1s struggle to justify the time investment, especially given the heavy workloads and inconsistent institutional requirements. Their limited understanding of OA routes and repository options as well as of other Open RRI themes also exposes a need for clearer guidance, harmonised terminology and accessible tools across institutions.

R1s additionally require training that is interactive, peer-centred and clearly relevant to their career paths. Self-paced formats alone are ineffective, and mixed-seniority groups can create barriers to participation. Commitment increases when training provenance is transparent and when concrete examples, projects and case scenarios show real benefits, from improved publications to better career outcomes. These insights imply that **policies must prioritise recognition, clarity and relevance to support meaningful engagement at the earliest career stage.**

Recommendations:

1. Ensure formal recognition and reduce time barriers

- Integrate ECTS-bearing modules as the default for R1 Open RRI training.
- Provide standardised ECTS validation templates for universities and research institutions.
- Issue micro-credentials, certificates, and digital badges throughout the learning journey, not only at the end.

2. Improve clarity and accessibility of Open RRI concepts

- Adopt harmonised glossaries across training materials on all Open RRI themes, e.g. for OA: green/gold/diamond; for citizen science: contributory/participatory/collaborative

⁶ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/career-development>

methodologies; for research integrity: culture-sensitive/ethical peer-to-peer/ethical mentee-supervisor research cooperations, etc).

- Develop a shared database listing repository options, institutional agreements and diamond OA venues.
- Clearly state institution, project and funding provenance on all learning materials on Open RRI themes to enhance commitment, trust and time investment.

3. Tailor training to R1 learning preferences

- Offer microlearning units including gamified activities such as short videos, podcasts, flashcards, micro-quizzes, linked to ECTS modules.
- Add light interaction in self-paced courses via mini-quizzes, reflection prompts, short peer exchanges.
- Ensure sufficient cohort size for group activities and create peer-only spaces early in the learning journey.
- Provide shared activity templates and facilitation guides to help smaller or lower-capacity institutions implement interactive components.

4. Ensure relevance of Open RRI across career paths

- Integrate career-relevant case studies from research-intensive industry, General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) roles, innovation, and public-sector research.
- Share success stories showing how Open RRI skills improved publications and other research outputs and processes, helped secure grants or aided job transitions.
- Provide ready-to-use materials and examples that institutions with fewer resources can adopt to ensure equitable quality, including materials to train librarians and other research support staff

B. FROM EMERGING RESEARCHERS TO ESTABLISHED ONES (R2 & R3)

Mid-career researchers (R2 and R3) face both structural and cultural obstacles to adopting Open RRI. While funder mandates, institutional policies, and emerging career pathways in, for example, data stewardship or research management act as enablers, these are weakened by high Article Processing Charge (APC) costs, confusion around OA options, and limited awareness of Open RRI themes in general. Persistent references to the research hard/ technical skills over soft/interpersonal ones, publication-centric mindsets and habits raise pressure to publish in high-impact journals. Reliance on publication quantity and journal prestige in recruitment, and inconsistent institutional enforcement continue to overshadow Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA⁷) and Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA⁸) principles and create a clear gap between policy and practice.

Sustainable cultural change requires incentives and assessment to match training messages. Unless Open RRI knowledge is embedded into assessment, promotion, and supervisory expectations in a holistic way, R2–R3 researchers receive conflicting signals about what institutions actually value. Training must include Principal Investigators (PIs) and senior academics to ensure alignment within research teams. Practical tools such as journal quality checking, repository workflows, curated agreement lists, Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and tools relevant to other Open RRI themes combined with peer communities can support consistent adoption. Ultimately, effective transformation depends on coherent incentives, aligned evaluation systems, and institutional support structures that empower mid-career researchers to lead and model Open RRI practices.

⁷ <https://www.coara.org/>

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/e69aff11-4494-4e5f-866c-694539a3ea26_en?filename=ec_rtd_commitments-reform-research-assessment.pdf

Recommendations:

1. Make Open RRI the default in workflows

- Implement rights-retention policies and integrate immediate self-archiving into trusted repository workflows.
- Provide curated journal agreements databases and discipline-specific repository guidance.
- Provide ready-to-use templates, guidance, and post-training peer communities to support consistent group-level implementation on different Open RRI themes.

2. Align leadership, assessment and career progression

- Complement the use of quantitative metrics such as number of publications in indexed journals, or journals with a high impact factor, with rewarding openness, RRI, reproducibility and team Open Science compliance.
- Train evaluators and committees to assess quality and contribution, not venue prestige.
- Require emerging and established researchers to complete at least the most relevant Open RRI training and periodic refreshers, e.g. on leadership and mental health skills for emerging PIs who start managing their first teams.
- Integrate Open RRI compliance into performance reviews, mentoring responsibilities, and promotion criteria.

3. Support cultural change through community and mentoring

- Create peer mentoring programmes, buddy systems and post-training communities of practice.
- Recognise and reward Open RRI Champions through internal awards or service credits.
- Integrate wellbeing and community-building activities into Open RRI training offerings to reduce isolation and encourage sustained engagement.

4. Remove financial and structural barriers to compliance

- Invest and promote the usage of open infrastructures such as repositories, preprint servers, scholarly datasets.
- Publish and maintain an institutional journal agreements database and promote tools such as DOAJ⁹, the Journal Checker Tool¹⁰ and CC Licence Chooser¹¹.
- Provide targeted support for R2/R3s managing projects with complex Open RRI obligations.

C. LEADING RESEARCHERS (R4)

Senior researchers known as R4 academics face distinct challenges in adopting Open RRI practices: their needs are shaped by leadership responsibilities, limited time, and disciplinary cultures that often prioritise publication prestige over Open RRI practices. While motivated by staying credible as mentors, improving supervision quality, and enhancing their leadership profile, they struggle with evolving expectations around a variety of Open RRI themes. Long self-paced or generic courses are largely ineffective for this category as **senior academics require short, contextualised, discipline-specific sessions embedded into existing responsibilities**. Their engagement improves when training delivers immediate practical benefits, e.g. for upcoming grants, publications, and team management, and when institutional infrastructure (repositories,

⁹ <https://doaj.org/>

¹⁰ <https://journalcheckertool.org/>

¹¹ <https://creativecommons.org/chooser/>

ethics support, data protection office (DPO) services) ensures that applying Open RRI principles is feasible in daily workflows.

At the same time, systemic barriers persist. The latter are hierarchical research cultures, early/mid-career researchers' uneven Open RRI knowledge, and weak alignment between institutional expectations and actual evaluation and promotion practices. Mandatory participation for leadership roles, accreditation mechanisms, and clear incentives can help overcome these barriers. Strategies that involve senior researchers directly in co-creation, train-the-trainer formats, and cross-generational sessions reinforce ownership and cultural change. Effective implementation requires institutions to embed Open RRI into governance structures, provide templates and decision aids, and create communities of practice (CoPs) where senior academics can exchange experience and conduct responsible research leadership.

Recommendations:

1. Embed Open RRI into leadership and governance

- Integrate Open RRI training into existing leadership programmes, committees (e.g. the Ethics Committee) and departmental onboarding, rather than generating new documentation or new governance structures, especially in institutions with fewer resources.
- Make participation in Open RRI training mandatory for PhD supervision, committee membership, or major grant leadership.
- Offer accreditation, certificates, and recognition (e.g. Open RRI Champion) to incentivise participation and reinforce expectations.
- Organise regular exchanges with research-intensive industry and other local non-academic actors to explore different career paths and skills needed for the researchers, especially for early career researchers under supervision.

2. Provide short, practical, context-rich training formats

- Deliver short, applied sessions linking Open RRI to grants and research practice.
- Use scenario-based workshops, coaching, and conference-adjacent sessions tailored to discipline-specific realities.
- Avoid long self-paced modules, prioritise interactive, face-to-face or hybrid formats that accommodate senior researchers' schedules.

3. Strengthen tools, templates, and support infrastructure

- Ensure access to publication and data repositories, ethics guidance, data management plan (DMP) templates, authorship checklists, and GDPR/DPO support.
- Promote the usage of open infrastructures and tools whenever possible.
- Provide discipline-specific examples and ready-to-use decision aids for supervision, publication, and data workflows.
- Develop intermediate roles (e.g., gender equality agents, DPOs, citizen science coordinators, data stewards, librarians qualified in Open RRI matters) to translate training into daily research practice and support senior staff.

4. Build CoPs and cross-generational engagement

- Create face-to-face CoPs for senior researchers to discuss cases and share expertise.
- Organise mixed sessions with early-career researchers, using interactive, facilitated formats to enhance engagement.
- Empower senior academics to co-develop training materials and participate in train-the-trainer programmes, strengthening institutional Open RRI leadership.

To facilitate the adoption of these recommendations, PATTERN developed:

- Individual, **tailored training plans in 14 pilot institutions**, which can serve as inspiration for other institutions to develop their own training plans.
- Free of charge, **open access training modules** strengthening researchers' transferable skills around eight Open RRI themes:
 - *Open Access;*
 - *FAIR Research Data Management;*
 - *Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion in Research;*
 - *Research Integrity;*
 - *Citizen Science;*
 - *Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results;*
 - *Leadership and Mental Health;*
 - *Science Communication.*

These training modules were tested, refined and evaluated in two LCs.

- An interconnected **digital environment** (OpenPlato and Projects Platforms) adapted to project-based learning methodology and accompanied by the modules' sustainability plan.
- A set of **co-created policy recommendations and policy briefs** for various stakeholders, including policymakers, research funding organisations, research performing organisations, research staff and students at universities and research institutions.
- **Dissemination and advocacy** actions to promote the uptake of the recommendations and modules, and the improvement of policies at all levels.
- A **community** of universities and research institutions willing to create and deliver comprehensive trainings on Open RRI themes to their researchers and students. The community involves PATTERN partners but aims to expand to the wider community during and beyond the project lifetime, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and re-usability of the training materials developed.

During the final year of project implementation, the PATTERN consortium focused on developing the sustainability plans for the digital environment and the training modules co-created and piloted. The project outputs dedicated specifically to sustainability planning, are available on the [PATTERN Zenodo community](#).

The project outputs related to this Policy Brief can also be consulted on the PATTERN Zenodo community:

- [D4.1 State-of-the-art Analysis: Mapping of the policy landscape for learning opportunities for researchers on Open and Responsible Research and Innovation](#)
- [D4.2 First PATTERN Policy Brief](#)
- [D4.3 Second PATTERN Policy Brief](#)
- [D4.4 PATTERN Policy Recommendations](#)

PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGIES

The PATTERN (Open and Responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks) project aimed to promote the practice of Open RRI by developing and piloting training activities aimed at researchers at all stages of their careers.

The training strengthens researchers' transferable skills to support their career development, improve research capacities and outcomes, and stimulate innovation. These training activities were co-designed with and implemented by 14 pilot research performing organisations to improve the excellence of the science conducted, tackle pressing societal challenges and strengthen collaboration that benefits both science and society. The training was developed around eight main transferable skills in the context of Open RRI mentioned above. PATTERN quality assurance was based on double testing cycle in different countries and (flagship) universities around Europe.

The consistent methodology applied in PATTERN was based on four subsequent Running Phases:

1. **Consolidation of knowledge** on existing trainings and policies featuring the need for training on Open RRI themes to identify the potential for new training activities for researchers at all stages of their careers and linking it to the policy component;
2. **Developing PATTERN training activities and platform** that enable learners to easily access and make use of those materials in the long-term;
3. **Testing and evaluating PATTERN training modules** to further refine them;
4. **Finding evidence for policy development.**

In addition, there was a horizontal Holding Phase which is a **co-creation and co-design** of methodological approach across all activities. Dissemination, communication and engagement activities also assure widespread outreach of the projects' results and outcomes to reach its impacts.

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME	Open and Responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks (PATTERN)
COORDINATOR	Alessio Livio Spera, Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (APRE), Rome, Italy spera@apre.it
CONSORTIUM	Aarhus University – AU - Denmark Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea – APRE – Italy Data Archiving and Networked Services – DANS – the Netherlands European Association of Research Managers and Administrators – EARMA - Belgium Fondation Européenne de la Science – ESF –France Globaz, S.A. – LOBA – Portugal

Learning Planet Institute – LPI –France

OPENAIRE AMKE – OpenAIRE - Greece

Ruđer Bošković Institute – RBI - Croatia

Stichting SciLink – SciLink - the Netherlands

Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati di Trieste – SISSA –Italy

Università Vita-Salute San-Raffaelle – UniSR - Italy

Universidade do Minho – UMinho - Portugal

Zentrum Für Soziale Innovation GmbH – ZSI – Austria

OpenAIRE Affiliated Entities:

University of Helsinki – UHelsinki –Finland

Trinity College Dublin - TCD – Ireland

Izmir Institute of Technology – IZTECH - Türkiye

University of Debrecen – UDebrecen - Hungary

PANEPITIMIO PATRON - HEAL-Link - Greece

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BUDGET

EU contribution: 3 499 742.50 €

WEBSITE

<https://www.pattern-openresearch.eu/>

FOR MORE INFORMATION

Contact (project coordination team):
 Alessio Livio Spera, spera@apre.it
 Stefania Laneve, laneve@apre.it
 Francesca Foliti, foliti@apre.it

FURTHER READING

All project outputs are available on the PATTERN Zenodo community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/pattern/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

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